

CURE KINETICS OF BIO-BASED POLYESTER RESINS USING NITROXIDE MEDIATED HYDROPEROXIDE INITIATORS

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1. Introduction

Partially renewable bio-based polyester resins currently manufactured by Ashland® have been in use since 2003 in large farm tractor applications. The commercial resin used in this study is Envirez 70301™, which is based off of the same high maleate synthesis process used to manufacture Envirez 1807™, the polyester resin currently being used by John Deere® for the manufacture of large combine and tractor components such as hoods, roofs, and fenders. This paper looks at the cure kinetics and thermo-mechanical analysis of jute fiber reinforced composites using Arkema's IS-300™ nitroxide mediated hydroperoxide and Envirez 70301 bio-based polyester resin. The curing process is generally initiated using dibenzoyl peroxide (BPO) per the manufacturer's recommendation [1]. The resin has previously been used with methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP) and tert-Butyl peroxybenzoate (TBPB). The results demonstrate a cure which is more controlled with a lower exothermic reaction at a lower temperature. The system is cured at a temperature below 100°C in order to prevent the evolution of water from the jute fiber. It will be assumed that the fabric used will be left in an open environment where pre-drying and conditioning will not be used. Using the nitroxide reversible-termination capability of the nitroxide mediated hydroperoxide, the resin and fiber system becomes capable of being developed into a pre-impregnated fabric for use in automotive and housing applications using jute cloth, allowing a lower energy requirement to manufacture sustainable composites. This will significantly reduce the carbon footprint of various manufactured items, increase biodegradability and compostability of various components, and prevent increased landfill volume.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Resin

The unsaturated polyester resin used for this research is Ashland's Envirez 70301™ soybean oil based resin. This resin is manufactured using the "high maleate" process [2, 3], which allows the use of oil with low reactivity to make a highly reactive resin. The resin contains soybean oil and corn/sugar cane-derived ethanol, which gives the resin a 22% renewable content. The resin has a viscosity of 2200 cps at room temperature (25°C). The other components of the resin are maleic anhydride and glycol. Styrene is used as the monomer, but only at a level of 29.5% by weight rather than 50% as in many fully petrochemical based unsaturated polyester resins. The use of bio-based polyester and epoxy resins have blossomed as the ability to incorporate the plant-based oils into the process had become well developed over the past ten years [4, 5].

2.2 Controlled / Living Radical Polymerization

Controlled / living radical polymerization (CRP/LRP) began as early as 1980 with the development of nitroxide mediated initiators in 1994 [6]. The purpose of LRP initiators is to allow chain growth, control over molecular weight and distribution, as well as prevent transfer and termination or chain breaking [7]. This process allows for chain end functionalization, removal of alkoxyamine functional groups, and an increase in thermal stability of the resulting polymer [8]. This reversible equilibrium allows a reversible equilibrium to exist between propagating and dormant states. This allows a cross-coupling of growing radicals preventing self-termination [9]. Through this initiator process, the simplest process can occur through a polymerization of a simple

monomer and initiator mix, although it is restricted to the types of monomers, generally styrenic and acrylic.

2.3 Initiator

Developed in 2010, the initiator, Arkema's IS-300™, has shown increase in fatigue life, increased toughness, and controlled radical polymerization. This initiator is a nitroxide-mediated hydroperoxide which allows some of the free radicals to bond with the monomer and allow polymerization, but also provides nitroxides which bind to the same unsaturation points. The nitroxide mediated cumene hydroperoxide used in this research, IS-300™, is a unique molecule which was designed by Arkema for the purpose of using a single, stable, and freely reactive unpaired electron to pair up with carbon – centered radicals only [6]. This binding is a reversible act where the addition of thermal energy will cause the nitroxide to detach and allow the hydroperoxide free radical to attach. This will allow a completion of the polymerization process and achieve maximum cross-link density in the cured resin based upon the heat added. The initiator also assists in controlling the exothermic heat release during the curing process which prevents generation of water vapor during the cure process. Dibenzoyl peroxide (Luperox® A98 – 50/50 by weight mix with styrene) has been used as the initiator for this resin in the past, but several others have been investigated. Previous research by the authors include the use of methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP – Luperox® DDM-9) and tert-butyl peroxybenzoate (TBPB – Luperox® P) [10].

Figure 1 – Cumene hydroperoxide

2.4 Promoter

This research uses cobalt (II) ethylhexanoate, also known as cobalt octoate. This is a promoter designed to cleave the hydroperoxides into free radicals [11]. This will allow the nitroxides and free

radicals to reach an equilibrium allowing a portion of the resin and monomer to cross-link, but not to the gelation or vitrification point. This promoter consists of a pair of 2-Ethylhexanoic acid molecules forming a bond with cobalt at the single oxygen bond. Cobalt octoate is a lipophilic derivative designed to be soluble in nonpolar organic solvents. The hydroperoxide is decomposed into alkoxy and peroxy free radicals [12]. The decomposition follows one of the following pathways shown in Equations 1 or 2.

Figure 2 Cobalt (II) ethylhexanoate

2.5 Fabric/Fibers

Natural jute fiber cloth was used in the raw form as shipped. Samples were conditioned at 25°C / 60% relative humidity. The fabric is sold in a commercially available form, standard burlap cloth [13]. This was chosen because of the wide availability, very low cost, and sustainable/recyclable nature of the fibers. The processing of the cloth does not require specialty clothing, respirators, or hardened cutting equipment as the fibers are not hazardous, do not pose an inhalation hazard, and are not abrasive to milling / cutting equipment.

2.6 Fabrication Process – Composite Panels

Issues arise when curing composites made from unmodified or raw natural fibers when not

desiccated or oven-dried to remove the absorbed moisture. When curing raw natural fiber laminates, the moisture can be trapped by gelled resin and cause issues with proper curing, delaminating layers, or de-bonding matrix from the fibers. In order to alleviate this issue, the fibers must be cured at a temperature lower than 100°C. When this is not possible, the ability to cure the resins in a more controlled manner at a lower temperature with less autocatalytic exothermic heat release is needed. The approach taken by this paper is to assume that the fiber will not be treated or pre-conditioned in any way other than that as shipped by the manufacturer. This jute fiber cloth (burlap) was purchased in the United States, but it is sourced from regions in India and Bangladesh.

2.7 Curing process – Neat Resin

The resin samples were measured out in 50 gram batches with a concentration of 1 part per hundred resin (phr) initiator to determine the optimum cure kinetics. Previous work with the resins using MEKP, TBPB, and a 50/50 mix of the two as the initiator showed the decomposition of the peroxide at high heating rates caused an excessive exothermic release during fabrication compared to the exothermic peak for IS-300™ as shown in Figure 1.

Table 3. Cure Parameters

Initiator	Mix Ratio	Cure Temp.	Cure Time (minutes)	Post Cure (min / °C)
TBPB	100:1	110 °C	60	None
MEKP	100:1	110 °C	60	None
IS300	100:1	140 °C	60	None
IS300	100:1: 0.2	85°C / 100°C	30 / 60	30/60/90 @ 140°C

2.8 Fabricated panels

Jute/Envirez 70301™ panels were made by compression molding. A Wabash 30 ton heated press was used to form 254mm x 254mm panels of 5mm thickness using 10 layers of burlap fabric. The layers of fabric were manually coated with the resin mixture on both sides, then the layers were assembled into 10 ply sheets. Those layups were then placed into a vacuum bag formed from high-temperature bagging film, degassed, and heat sealed

on all four sides. The panels were machined into dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) testing shapes using a Next Wave Automation CNC Router with V-Carve software. Several of the samples were then post cured in an oven at 140°C for time rates of 30, 60, and 90 minutes.

Table 4. Initiator versus Pressure

Initiator	Temp (°C)	Mold Pressure (kN)	Plate Size (cm ²)	Clamping Force (kPa)
TBPB	110	8.90	400	215.5
MEKP	110	8.90	400	215.5
TBPB	110	13.34	400	323.2
MEKP	110	13.34	400	323.2
IS300	85	26.70	645	413.9
IS300	85	26.70	645	413.9
IS300	100	26.70	645	413.9
IS300	100	26.70	645	413.9

2.9 Sample Preparation and Testing

DMA samples were tested to ASTM D-4065-06, where the samples were cut to 63mm x 14.26 ±0.34mm x 4.2mm ±0.43mm. The thickness was only machined to provide a consistent thickness, preventing the loss of any jute fiber. The thickness was not overly modified and allowed to remain as close to “as molded” as possible. DMA results were performed to determine the T_g, and storage/loss moduli. The samples were tested on a TA Instruments Q800 DMA in a dual cantilever apparatus. The tests were performed at 1Hz with a deflection of 15 μm. The temperature range was 30°C to 190°C.

DSC testing was performed on the uncured resin samples using a TA Instruments Q1000 with aluminum hermetic pans perforated with a vent hole. The dynamic temperature ramp rates were 2° C, 5° C, and 10° C per minute. The isothermal temperatures were 110 °C, 120 °C, and 130 °C for 120 minutes or until heat flow returned to a constant value. Samples were placed in the cell at a point where the isothermal temperature was stabilized to ensure the temperature ramp did not affect the results. Sample mass was 11.5mg ± 0.4 mg to ensure comparable results. Samples were run with and without promoter to determine the effects on peak

exothermic reaction temperature. DSC results were analyzed using the Specialty Library® software provided by TA Instruments. The dynamic curves were analyzed using the “Thermal Stability Kinetics Analysis” method. This model utilizes the Ozawa model and assumes the degree of reaction is a constant and is independent of the heating rate at maximum exothermic peak. The Ozawa model uses heating rates between 1°C and 10°C. The activation energy is found by determining the slope of the Ozawa plot [14, 15, 16]. β indicates heating rate, E is activation energy, T is peak temperature in Kelvin, and R is the universal gas constant.

$$Z = \frac{\beta E e^{E/RT}}{RT^2} \quad (3)$$

$$k(T) = Z e^{\frac{-E}{RT}} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T)(1 - \alpha) \quad (5)$$

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed using a TA Instruments Q500 machine with platinum pans. The temperature ramp rate was set at 5°C / minute during dynamic portions and allowed to equilibrate at the desired isothermal temperature by stopping the ramp at 5 °C before the isothermal temperature. This prevented the furnace temperature from surpassing the isothermal temperature before the end of the isothermal time period. Samples were kept at 12.0 mg ± .25 mg to ensure comparable results.

3. Results

3.1 Results – Neat Resin - DSC

The resin was mixed in small batches with and without promoter. All of the samples used in this work were mixed with 1 part per hundred (phr) initiator and 0.2 phr cobalt octoate promoter. Varied temperature ramp rates were run to determine the optimum cure rates. The exothermic peak in the samples with promoter show a maximum chemical reaction and crosslinking below the 100°C temperature point. The heat flow from the compression mold platens through the resin and fibers are determined by heat flow characteristics,

but is assumed to have a temperature increase well above the ramp rate possible on the DSC.

Promoter	Temp Ramp	Peak Exo. Temp (°C)	Onset Temp
CO OCT	2°C / min	84.5	69.6
	5°C / min	97.5	78.5
	10°C / min	105.6	84.2
None	2°C / min	127.6	117.2
	5°C / min	139.2	126.1
	10°C / min	151.0	136.1

Table 1 – DSC cure results

The platens on the compression mold machine are pre-heated and do not allow the composite sample to heat gradually. This rate is well above the capabilities of the DSC to test. Further study to determine the actual heating rate will be conducted at a later time.

Fig.3 – DSC – Dynamic ramp without Promoter

The samples with and without promoter were tested to determine whether the promoter would bring the optimum curing temperature as shown by maximum exothermic reaction below 100°C. This is important to prevent the moisture which had been absorbed by the fibers from outgassing as vapor during the curing process.

Fig. 4 – DSC – Dynamic ramp with Promoter

As shown in Figure 2, all three temperature ramp rates have a peak exothermic reaction below the 100°C threshold while none of the unpromoted resins fell below the 100°C mark. The curing process in the vacuum ovens, compression mold, and forced-air ovens all heat the samples at a rate well above 10°C per minute due to the thickness.

	Act. Energy	Std. Dev. AE	Pre-Exp. Factor	Std. Dev. PEF	60 min Half Life Temp
CO OCT	76.4	2.74%	10.34	2.94%	52.0
None	91.6	8.56%	11.08	9.06%	94.5

Table 2 – DSC cure kinetics – dynamic

As shown by the exothermic peaks, the heat generated by MEKP, TBPB, and a 50/50 mix of MEKP and TBPB are substantially higher than the nitroxide mediated IS-300. Although the cure occurs more quickly, the MEKP is prone to causing excessive heat build-up during the cycle. While this may not be an issue for thin items, bulkier items will store more thermal energy and accelerate the rate even faster due to a build-up of excess thermal energy. This is the largest concern with the manufacture of thicker components and part of the reason for the development of the IS300 initiator by Arkema. As can be assumed and will be the subject

of future testing, the temperature increase will be more dramatic as the sample thickness increases. It will be determined what relationship exists between the bio-based resin, jute fiber, and exothermic reaction and calculate what detriment or improvement the reaction has.

Fig. 5 - 120°C Isothermal DSC scans of Envirez 70301™ resin with 1phr initiator

The cure kinetics were determined by use of the TA Instruments Specialty Library using the Ozawa method described earlier in Section 2.6. The following are the conversion tables generated by the Ozawa model using the dynamic heating rates.

Fig. 6 – Percent cure versus Time – No Promoter

Fig. 7 – Percent cure versus Time – Promoter added

Fig. 8 – Tan delta curves / peaks 85°C / 30 min

IS300 only	IS300 + Cobalt Octoate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E: 91.6 kJ/mole ± 8.51% Log Z: 11.08 1/min ± 8.99% 60 min half-life: 94.5°C Enthalpy: 171.7 J/g ± 11.19% Conversion: Peak (auto) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E: 76.5 kJ/mole ± 2.62% Log Z: 10.35 1/min ± 2.77% 60 min half-life: 52.0°C Enthalpy: 297.7 J/g ± 9.66% Conversion: Peak (auto)

Table 4: Ozawa parameters

Fig.9 - DMA - 85°C/30 min

3.2 Results – Neat Resin - DMA

DMA testing of the composite samples focused on the storage modulus and tan delta peak. This was to determine the overall strength of the composite and glass transition temperature. As can be shown in Figure 7, the increase in tan delta peak coincides with the increase in post-curing temperature. The graph shown is that of the samples cured at 85°C for 30 minutes in compression mold and post cured at 140°C for 30, 60, and 90 minutes.

These results are shown here as the cure cycle just described demonstrates the greatest and largest increase in storage modulus. The tan delta peaks demonstrate a consistent increase in glass transition temperature with increased post curing time.

Fig.10 - DMA - 100°C/60 min

4. Conclusion

Allowing the composite to cure at a lower temperature and time with a longer post-cure duration will provide for a composite with the highest storage modulus. This is due in part to the quick cure caused by the rapid heat transfer from the press platens to the composite panel. The thickness of the samples was partially determined by the viscosity change in the resin as it began to flow out of the fiber.

The use of IS-300™ initiator will allow the better control of curing which will increase component thermo-mechanical properties and further increase the service life of natural fiber composites, more especially so with the use of a metal salt promoter, cobalt octoate in this research. The increased toughness will allow the matrix to remain undamaged longer and prevent moisture uptake into the composite and prolong the life of the composite component.

The decrease in thermal energy required to cure the composite will also decrease the energy used for fabrication. This will reduce the overall carbon footprint of the composite and aid in making the process more sustainable.

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